

SHORT COMMUNICATION

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF SORGHUM/SOYABEAN INTERCROP SYSTEMS BY PARTIAL BUDGET IN THE GUINEA SAVANNAH OF NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Five sorghum/soyabean planting schedules intercrop were evaluated in a field experiment at Mokwa (Guinea savannah) in Nigeria, during the 2012 and 2013 cropping seasons with a view of determining the planting schedule that will result in the highest net benefits. Experimental design was randomized complete block (RCB) with three replicates. Soyabean variety TGX1019-2EB was drilled on the crest of the ridge, while sorghum seedlings were transplanted on the lower side of the ridge. The following sorghum/soyabean intercrop treatments were evaluated: (1) Sorg + Soy 0DAPS: Sorghum seedlings intercropped with soyabean at 0 day after planting soyabean, (2) Sorg + Soy 14DAPS: Sorghum seedlings intercropped with soyabean at 14 days after planting soyabean, (3) Sorg + Soy 28DAPS: Sorghum seedlings intercropped with soyabean at 28 days after planting soyabean. Sole soyabean and sole sorghum were also planted as treatments 4 and 5 respectively. Results obtained indicated that the treatment Sorg + Soy 0DAPS gave the highest net benefit of N798, 000 and N287, 150 in 2012 and 2013 respectively.

KEYWORDS: Sorghum, Soyabean, Intercrop, Total extra cost, Extra benefits, Net benefits.

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INTRODUCTION

In almost all peasants cropping system intercropping predominates. The most important reason for the persistence of this farming practice are that gross return per unit area of land is usually higher under intercropping than in sole cropping. It also helps in the control of erosion and weeds and brings about even distribution of labour (Okigbo and Greenland, 1976). Yusuf *et al.* (2009) reported that planting of cassava at 28 Days Before Planting Soyabean resulted in the highest yields of the component crops. Yusuf *et al.* (2012) also reported that maize should be planted at 14 Days Before Planting Soyabean, for optimum yields of the component crops in a maize/soyabean planting schedule intercrop. Soyabean is an important non-meat source of protein. It is reported to contain about 40% protein, 20% oil, 30% carbohydrate, excellent amount of fiber, vitamins and mineral (IITA, 2009). The Guinea savannah is best suited for soyabean production in Nigeria, yet many farmers in this agro-ecological zone have not incorporated soyabean in to their cropping system. One of the challenges that hinder the cultivation of soyabean in this zone is the lack of information about the appropriate planting schedule required, for intercropping of soyabean with cereals crop like sorghum for optimum net benefits from the component crops. This experiment was therefore carried out to provide this information. The objective of this experiment was to determine the sorghum/soyabean planting schedule intercrop system required for optimum net benefits.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

A field experiment was conducted at the National Cereals Research Institute at Mokwa (Guinea savannah agro-ecological zone of Nigeria), during the 2012 and 2013 cropping seasons. The experiment was planted on ridges on a 14 x 38m land area. Sorghum seedlings (Red seeded photo-period sensitive farmers variety), were intercropped with soyabean variety TGX 1019-2EB on the following Days After Planting Soyabean (DAPS): (1) 0DAPS i.e. 22nd and 27th of July 2012 and 2013 respectively, (2) 14 DAPS i.e. 5th and 10th of August in 2012 and 2013 respectively, (3) 28DAPS i.e. 19th and 24th of August in 2012 and 2013 respectively, (4) Sole soyabean planted on the 22nd and 23rd of July in 2012 and 2013 respectively, (5) All sorghum seedlings were obtained from a sole sorghum plot planted in both years on June the 15th. Experimental design was randomize complete block (RCB) with three replicates. Soyabean seeds were planted on the crest of each ridge, while sorghum seedlings were planted on the lower side of each ridge. Soyabean plant spacing was 5 x 75cm (266,666plants/ha), while the sorghum plant spacing was 100 x 75 cm (13,333 plants/ha x 2): sorghum plants were thinned to two plants per stand. The gross plot (4 x 3m) consisted of 4 ridges, while the net plot (2 x 1m) consisted of the two central ridges of each plot. N P K were band applied to both crops at the rate of 30 kg/ha at 2 weeks after planting. Weed control was achieved by hoe weeding at 3 and 6 weeks after planting. Crop yields were subjected to statistical analysis using analysis of variance (ANOVA) and significant means separated by the Duncan's Multiple Range

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Test (DMRT). The net benefits of intercropping soyabean with sorghum were computed using partial budget.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In 2012, the highest net benefit of N 798,000:00 was obtained from the intercrop treatment sorghum intercrop with soyabean at 0 Day After Planting Soyabean (i.e. Sorg + Soy 0DAPS) (Table 1). A net benefit of N129,080 was obtained from the sole soyabean treatment, which indicated that a net benefit of N668,920 was gained as a result of intercropping sorghum with soyabean at 0 DAPS. Similar trends were observed in 2013, with the highest net benefit of N289, 150 obtained from the treatment Sorg + Soy 0DAPS (Table 2). A net benefit of N258, 900 was obtained from the sole soyabean treatment, which indicated that a net benefit of N30, 250 was gained as a result of intercropping sorghum with soyabean at 0 DAPS. In conclusion, for optimum net benefit, sorghum seedlings should be intercropped with soyabean on soyabean planting day (i.e. Sorg + Soy 0DAPS).

Table 1: Economic analysis by partial budget

Treatments	Sorg Yields (Kg/ha)	Soy Yields (Kg/ha)	Gross benefits	Net benefits
	2012			
Sorg + Soy0DAPS	1130.0a	367.5	N848, 000	N798, 000
Sorg + Soy14DAPS	870.0ab	828.6	N252, 720	N202, 720
Sorg + Soy28DAPS	217.0b	1152.1	N252, 120	N202, 120
Sole soyabean	-	895.4	N179, 080	N129, 080
Sole sorghum	1202.5a	-	N120, 250	N70, 250

N.B.

N.S

- Extra costs:-Soyabean seeds/ha (50kg) = ₦ 10, 000, planting of soyabean = ₦ 5, 000, harvesting, threshing, winnowing and bagging of soyabean = ₦ 35, 000.
- Total extra cost = ₦ 50, 000
- Extra benefit: - Sorg yield x sorg field price + soy yield x soy field price.
- Net benefit :- Extra Benefit – Total Extra Cost
- Sorghum field price; ₦ 100/kg
- Soyabean field price; ₦ 200/kg
- Sorg :- Sorghum
- Soy :- Soyabean

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Table 2: Economic analysis by partial budget

Treatments	Sorg Yields (Kg/ha)	Soy —	Gross benefits	Net benefits
	2013			
Sorg + Soy0DAPS	1017.5b	1177.0b	N337, 150	N287, 150
Sorg + Soy14DAPS	797.0c	1283.5ab	N336, 400	N286, 400
Sorg + Soy28DAPS	690.5d	1245.5ab	N318, 150	N268, 150
Sole soyabean	-	1544.5a	N308, 900	N258, 900
Sole sorghum	1134.5a	-	N113, 450	N63, 450

N.B.

N.S

- Extra costs:-Soyabean seeds/ha (50kg) = ₦ 10, 000, planting of soyabean = ₦ 5, 000, harvesting, threshing, winnowing and bagging of soyabean = ₦ 35, 000.
- Total extra cost = ₦ 50, 000
- Extra benefit:- Sorg yield x sorg field price + Soy yield x soy field price
- Net benefit :- Extra Benefit – Total Extra Cost
- Sorghum field price; ₦ 100/kg
- Soyabean field price; ₦ 200/kg
- Sorg :- Sorghum
- Soy :- Soyabean

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